

Leibniz-Junior Research Group

Urban human-nature resonance for sustainability transformation

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)

URBNANCE Blog

<https://urbnance.ioer.info/en/blog/>

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Photo: K. Artmann

Inside me – inside us

Talking with the deer and rabbits
Cooking with the moon and the stars
Flowing in being, vibrating with the divine feminine
Infinite power and wisdom in our veins

The sparkle in my eyes shows of eternity
We are born in the light and by the fire
Facing the moon, Mother Earth in our womb
One out there in the forest with me and everything
Alone together with the entity of the magic energy

Green the frequency flows
From head to toe to the beat of the drum
In the circle the spiders dance
And weave their web of life
In resonance with the mystical world
Of fairies, goblins, animals, and stones

All join in a song of cosmic tones
From the bellies and eyes sparkles the moss green diamond
Dips the night in the baptism
Of life full of lust and wildness,
Gentleness and goodness – everything vibrates
Everything is, then, now and forever
Inside me - inside us

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If you have any comments or question on the essay, feel warmly invited to contact the author (m.artmann@ioer.de).

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